

Paper 15

**IMPULSIVE BUYING AND ROLE OF AI IN
PERSONALISED MARKETING: OPINION OF THE
YOUTH OF DAKSHINA KANNADA**

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Abstract

The market is an ever changing place. From the producers being the decision makers of the consumer's needs, to the consumers being treated as kings, the market has seen it all. With digitalisation and globalisation, the customers now, have a number of choices to choose from, while the producers or the sellers have to deal with a number of competitors. The consumers are more aware and specific about their needs and wants, pushing the sellers to use innovative marketing tools for their benefit. The sellers need to send the right message, to the right customer, at the right time-this can be easily done with the help of AI.

Marketing is no longer considered as the process of informing the consumers about a product. It is now a more detailed, rigorous and well-thought out process; of which the execution too is meticulous. There are various trends in marketing, out of which target marketing is the most prominent one. AI (Artificial Intelligence) is growing in prominence and is taking the load off of the marketers. This study mainly concentrates on understanding the concept of target marketing and the role of AI in target marketing. The study also focuses on the opinion of the youth on target marketing and its effectiveness as a marketing tool.

Keywords: impulsive buying, customers, advertising, marketing

1.Introduction

The market and the way it operates changes every year. A few years ago, the manufacturers or sellers decided the customer's choices for them. But now, the customers are treated as kings and are given with multiple options to choose from. With the changes in the economy, a lot has changed for the marketers and the consumers. The marketers now, need to woo the customers into buying their product, and sometimes even create a need for their product, that the customer does not really need. The consumers on the other hand, have multiple choices of the product they need and many sellers to buy it from. The consumers are usually aware of what they precisely need and are equipped to purchase the product that provides them the satisfaction.

The prominent change in the market is the importance given to the customers a few years ago versus now. The flywheel-and a subsequent focus on service have replaced the one-way direction of the funnel.

The difference is shown below in the diagram:

Diagram no. 01:

This change in the market place has resulted in the need for the change in the marketing tools. One of the most trending marketing tool of today is the targeted marketing or the personalised marketing. The marketers these days use the artificial intelligence to attract the customers with specified or personalised advertisements that are curated according to the recent searches of the targeted customer. The marketers lure the customers in, with a number of personalised offers, making the customers want to buy the product as soon as possible. This makes the whole process of purchasing a product more personal to the consumer, causing an increase in the sales. Amazon, the e-commerce giant was the first business to conceptualise and execute this idea, in the early 2000's.

Digitalisation has caused many changes in the way the things are being bought and sold. One of the major changes is the e-commerce websites. This form of shopping is the most hassle free one, which is the main reason why the youth are leaning more towards this form of shopping. Online shoppers are also more prone towards buying things on an impulse. This weakness is being cashed in by the marketers and producers.

2. Meaning

Using Artificial intelligence is now the latest trend in the marketing world. Though the practice of collecting the consumer behaviours for predicting the future trends has been in the market from almost 1998, collecting data in this day and age, has changed enormously. The Artificial Intelligence is being used in almost every industry. It collects the consumer data, paired with profile information and demographics. AI is the method of leveraging customer data and concepts like machine learning to anticipate the customer's next move and improve the customer's experience in shopping with a particular business. The AI continually adapts to the likes and dislikes of the consumers and tailors the recommendations as required.

Impulsive buying simply put, means unplanned purchasing. These are the buying decisions that are not made neither rationally or habitually and is not characterised by the extent of cognitions alone. The impulsive buying can be the result of various stimuli, such as, motivation and perception, the stimulation having to be stronger enough to overcome restraints, buying situations, impulsive behaviour in general and so on.

Stern (1962) has identified four distinct types of impulsive purchasing: planned, pure, reminder and suggestion impulse purchasing. Planned impulse purchasing is when the shoppers do not plan their purchases, but search for and take advantage of in-store promotions, thus maximising their buying power (Nesbitt-1959). Pure impulse purchasing occurs when consumers experience truly impulsive buying, the novelty or escape purchase breaks a normal buying pattern (Stern 1962, p. 59). Reminder impulsive purchasing occurs when the consumer is reminded of the need to buy an item upon seeing it. Suggestion buying is when the consumer sees the product and then visualises a need for it. (p. 59-60).

3.Literature review

- Beatty and Ferrel (1998) described that “impulse buying refers to immediate purchases which are without any pre-shopping objective either to purchase the specific product category or to fulfil a specific need. They explained that the impulse buying behaviour occurs after experiencing a buying desire by the shopper and without much reflection. The buying of an item which is out of stock and reminded during encountering the product are excluded from the purview of impulse buying.”
- According to Engel and Blackwell (1982) “impulse buying is an action undertaken without previously having been consciously recognised or a buying intention formed prior to entering the store.”
- Sanjiv Mehta, CEO & MD of Hindustan Unilever Ltd. Says, “the core of marketing hasn’t changed, but the way we communicate has changed marketing. It is morphing every day. That’s where the big shift has happened. The art of storytelling is very much there but how we tell the story and the medium through which we tell the story is the key. The big changes that will happen in marketing, just as in business, is artificial intelligence and machine learning.”
- Thomas H. Davenport states, “Contemporary marketing is increasingly quantitative, targeted, and tied to business outcomes. Ads and promotions are increasingly customised to individual consumers in real time. Companies employ multiple channels to get to customers, but all of them increasingly employ digital content. Company marketers still work with agencies, many of which have developed analytical capabilities of their own.”
- According to Xia and Monroe (2009), their study resulted that consumers with a shopping goal are more responsive towards promotional messages such as “pay less” and “discount” while consumers without shopping goal are responsive towards promotional messages such as “save more” and “free gift”. Xia and Monroe (2009, p.691) cited from (Monroe, 2003) that price promotion have several benefits such as to increase demand, adjust fluctuations in supply and demand, and increasing consumers’ purchasing over time.”

4.Objectives

- To analyse the role of artificial intelligence in personalised marketing.
- To study the impact of personalised advertisements on the purchasing behaviour of the youth.
- To understand the opinion of the youth on the use artificial intelligence in personalised marketing.

5.Methodology

- The primary data has been collected through questionnaires.
- The secondary data was collected from various journals and articles.

6.Scope

The study concentrates on the use of artificial intelligence only as a tool in the personalised marketing that is done in online marketing. The study analyses the impact of personalised marketing on the impulsive buying behaviour of the consumer, while shopping online. The respondents are selected randomly, and are in their late teens or early twenties, as they are considered as the youth for the sake of this study.

7.Results and Discussions

The total number of respondents was 100. The respondents were selected in a random manner, the only consideration being their age. The questionnaire was distributed, filled and collected physically.

The respondents were mainly from the Dakshina Kannada district and where of the age 15-26. This age range was chosen as it is the demographic of people that indulge in online shopping. Most of the respondents were of the age 23-26, which means, they were employed and spent their salary on buying the products. The least number of the respondents belonged to the category of 15-18 age range. The number of the female respondents was slightly higher than the male respondents. The same information is given below in the tabular form.

Table no. 01:

Age	Percentage	Gender	Percentage	Employment Status	Percentage
15-18	12	Male	41	Student	29
19-22	25	Female	59	Employed	71
23-26	63	Other	-		

*The percentage total is 100.

Majority of the respondents often shopped online and very few times they had their shopping list pre-determined. Most of them agreed to have purchased an item online, on an impulse.

Table no. 02:

Shop online	Percentage	Pre-determined list	Percentage	Impulse purchases	Percentage
Very often	55	Very often	15	Very often	18
Sometimes	27	Sometimes	57	Sometimes	59
Rarely	10	Rarely	19	Rarely	17
Never	8	Never	9	Never	6

The following table shows that the related advertisements and offers were the main reasons for the impulsive purchases. They did not think that they would have purchased the same item if they had physically gone shopping instead of the online shopping.

Table no. 03:

Motive for impulsive purchasing	Percentage	Purchases made due to the influence	Percentage	Physically purchase the same item	Percentage
Related advertisements	59	Very often	35	Yes	25
Offers	12	Sometimes	23	No	46
Discounts	23	Rarely	39		
Free shipping	3	Never	3	Maybe	29
Others	3				

Though they found that most of the times the advertisements were relevant to their searches, they did not however think that these related advertisements helped them to make rational decisions. The notification of these personalised advertisements were also seen as a nuisance by many and said that they didn't like receiving them.

Table no. 04:

Relevancy of the advertisements	Percentage	Help in making rational decisions	Percentage	Receiving notifications	Percentage
Very often	47	Very often	15	Very often	13
Sometimes	39	Sometimes	21	Sometimes	21
Rarely	12	Rarely	48	Rarely	29
Never	2	Never	16	Never	37

The younger generation of people knew about the use of Artificial Intelligence in marketing, though not in a detailed manner. They were aware that their moves on the internet were being followed and taken advantage of. Though they liked to get the personalised advertisements and offers, they were not too keen on having to compromise their privacy to receive it. They were of the view that these notifications were not worth compromising their privacy.

Table no. 05:

Awareness of AI in marketing	Percentage	Awareness of sharing personal data	Percentage	Favour towards sharing personal data	Percentage
Yes	46	Yes	51	Yes	63
No	24	No	20	No	18
Maybe, not sure	30	Maybe	29	I don't mind	100

8. Conclusion

With the changing times, the techniques and approach to marketing has changed for the general good. The consumers today are aware of more market tactics than our elder generations. This makes it hard for the marketers to sell the products. This is where the Artificial Intelligence comes into play. It plays an important role in marketing the products to the targeted consumers in an efficient manner, thus increasing the consumer base and the sales.

This however, is not the same view point the youth of today has, towards Artificial Intelligence and personalised marketing. Though these marketing tools make it easy for them to choose and buy what they want, the way they want to, it often tends to mislead them. The downhill in this is that the more and more people are being aware of it. The main issue is with the sharing of the privacy, without which the personalised marketing technique is spineless. Hence, the need to make the consumers feel safer about their privacy might become the immediate need in future. But as of now, Artificial Intelligence is making a huge impact on the buying behaviour of the consumers and the marketing tools.

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